

EFFECTS OF COUPLING AGENTS AND SURFACE TREATED CARBON NANOTUBES IN PET REGRANULATES DERIVED FROM BOTTLE WASTES

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1 General Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been intensively investigated in the field of polymer composites in the recent two decades. As commercially available CNTs are expensive materials research have been mainly focused on their application in high performance polymers. Effective introduction of CNTs into the polymer matrices is based on the proper interactions between nanotubes and polymer matrix besides strong ability of CNTs to agglomeration should also be decreased. Several methods have been developed for achieving the mentioned purposes but most of them can be carried out only in laboratory scale and conditions. Research has also begun in the field of engineering plastics for producing CNT containing composites but e.g. there are only a few scientific papers on PET meanwhile lots of patents have appeared worldwide. Application of polyethylene-terephthalate (PET) has been widely known in packaging and electronic industry and as a consequence municipal solid waste also contain a high amount of PET, therefore, its reuse can also have significance.

In our experimental work multi-walled carbon nanotubes have been applied in PET regranulates derived from water and refreshment bottle wastes. On the first hand the effects on carbon nanotube concentration have been investigated and on the second hand olefin-maleic-anhydride copolymer based coupling agents with different structures have been applied for treating the surface of the CNTs and the mechanical properties of the CNT/PET composites have also been studied. Results have also been compared to composites made from commercially available PET material.

2 Experimental

As polymer matrices commercially available PET (MFI=43g/10min at 260°C and 2.16kg, denoted later as PET-1) and PET regranulates derived from bottle wastes were used (MFI=22g/10min at 255°C and

2.16kg, denoted later as PET-2). PET regranulates from selective collection at our Department was a 1:1 mixture of bottles in blue and green colors.

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) were produced at 700°C by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process over Fe-Co bimetallic catalyst at the Institutional Department of Chemical Engineering (Institute of Chemical and Process Engineering, University of Pannonia, Veszprém, Hungary) [1]. Their diameter was between 10 and 20 nm and their average length was above 30 µm. The synthesized nanotubes were not separated from the talc support, thus the produced filler material consisted of 90 wt% MWCNTs and 10 wt% talc.

Experimental olefin-maleic-anhydride copolymer based coupling agents were applied in order to improve compatibility between the polymer and the nanotubes. Coupling agents of Fig. 1 were synthesized at our Department. Concentration of the coupling agents was selected to be equal in all the composite samples in order to make a correct comparison of their effectiveness. Surface of CNTs was covered by the coupling agent from the hydrocarbon solution of it. After the solvent had been evaporated out treated CNTs were dried at 110 °C for 2 hours and were introduced into the neat polymer in a LabTech LTE 20-44 type twin-screw extruder. Composition of the CNT/PET samples was represented in Table 1. The concentration of samples from PET regranulates was measured to be two times higher than for samples made from commercial PET at the same screw rotation speeds. That should be a consequence of easier homogenization experienced during production of CNT/PET waste composites probably related to enhanced interaction between the coupling agents on the CNT surface and the other additives in the regranulates. Extruded strings were mechanically tested after processing.

3 Results

Structure of the coupling agents significantly influenced the yield strength of CNT/PET composites (Fig.2.) both for commercially available and for PET bottle waste raw materials.

Effects of the coupling agents appeared during the processing of the composites too because treated carbon nanotubes could be introduced in different concentrations into the polymer melt of the commercial PET. CNT content in the composites of the lowest yield strength could be increased only to about 2wt%. That was two times higher than untreated CNT containing reference but strengthening effect of the CNTs could not be realized. That could be explained by weak interaction between the matrix and the CNTs and the additive only made processing easier. Best result was measured for CA-2 treated CNT/PET samples although CNT-content was almost the same as the reference had. So improvement could be connected to the coupling agent and not to the CNT-concentration.

In composites from PET bottle wastes all the coupling agents had positive effect on yield strength. Using CA-4 type coupling agent made a 50% increase compared to the untreated CNT/PET waste sample representing the influence of coupling agent and surface treatment. Polarity of the coupling agents played a significant role on the yield strength. The most advantageous effect was experienced with a coupling agent (CA-4) containing aromatic rings in one of the reagents applied for synthesis. Changes of other tensile properties (modulus, elongation at break) were also measured.

Based on the results it had been concluded that proper selection of the structure of the coupling agent and the processing conditions led to at least 10-30% improvement in the yield strength of the treated CNT/PET composites compared to the untreated CNT containing ones. Increase should probably be related to the enhancement in crystalline forming due to the coupling agent.

Yield strength of the products from PET waste – depending on the structure of the coupling agent–exceeded the yield strength of the composites made from original PET. That should probably be caused by the interaction among the coupling agent and the other additives (e.g. coloring additives) founded in the PET waste.

References

- [1] A. Szentes, G. Horváth” Role of catalyst support in the growth of multi-walled carbon nanotubes”.

Fig. 1. Structure of experimental olefin-maleic-anhydride copolymer based coupling agents (R_1 : alkyl chain with length of the olefin monomer; R_2 :alkyl chain with R_1-2 carbon number; a, b: 2-21; k: 0.2-2.0; l: 1-5; m: 1-5; n: 0.3-2.0)

Table 1. Composition of surface treated CNT containing PET composites

sample sign	polymer type	CNT-content, wt. %	coupling agent
COMP-1	PET-1	1.0	-
COMP-2	PET-1	2.0	CA-1
COMP-3	PET-1	1.2	CA-2
COMP-4	PET-1	1.3	CA-3
COMP-5	PET-1	2.1	CA-4

COMP-6	PET-2	2.6	-
COMP-7	PET-2	2.4	CA-1
COMP-8	PET-2	3.5	CA-2
COMP-9	PET-2	3.5	CA-3
COMP-10	PET-2	3.1	CA-4

Fig. 2. Yield strength of extruded CNT/PET composites

